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Cc: [Magdalena.Skarżyńska](#); [Anjum.Muna](#)
Subject: IMPART End meeting - save the time and date
Start: tuesday 2. mars 2021 12:00:00
End: tuesday 2. mars 2021 16:00:00
Location: Teams

Dear members of the IMPART consortium,

I hope this email finds you well.

We have ended our OH EJP project as of December 2020, but there are still a few tasks that needs to be fulfilled.

Thank you very much for replying to the Doodle poll that we sent out before Christmas. We hereby invite you to attend the End Meeting of IMPART on Tuesday March 2nd. Please reserve the time in your calendar for this occasion.

We would prefer to use the platform Teams for this meeting, please inform me if this is difficult for you/your institute and let me know which platform you prefer.

Kind regards,

Jannice

On behalf of the IMPART WP leaders

Microsoft Teams meeting

Join on your computer or mobile app

Click here to join the meeting <https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ameeting_OWQ0YTFIZDYtNWRIZS00ODQ0LThhZjMtNjdIMTRIZGY1ZGRi%40thread.v2/0?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%22885830bf-ea2c-4b92-87a6-6a9afa4d7334%22%2c%22Oid%22%3a%2286dbba8a-df52-46ac-8a34-a89723aec19d%22%7d>

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